

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20595055

Demographic Variables as Correlates of Marital Satisfaction Among Couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated Demographic Variables as Correlates of Marital Satisfaction Among Couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational des. The research examined how gender and family size correlate with marital satisfaction. Data were collected from 365 married couples across ten council wards. The instruments used for data collection were the Demographic Variables of Married Couples Scale (DVMCS) and Marital Satisfaction Scale (MSS). Reliability coefficient of DVMCS were 0.96 while the MSS yielded 0.98. Data was analysed to answer the research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correction was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that gender had significance positive relationship with marital satisfaction of couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State. On the other hand, family size was found to have a significant negative relationship with marital satisfaction of couples. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others first, counsellor should educate spouses on gender equality stressing that female children are equal to male children, secondly counsellors should educate couples on family planning and stress management in marriage.

Keywords: Demographic variables, Gender, Family size, Marital satisfaction, Couples

INTRODUCTION

Marital satisfaction is a crucial aspect of a successful and healthy marriage, but many couples globally face challenges that hinder them from achieving it. Despite the importance of marital satisfaction, research has shown that many couples in Nigeria experience low levels of satisfaction in their marriages, leading to increased conflict, separation, and divorce. The prevalence of marital dissatisfaction has been linked to various factors, including communication problems, lack of intimacy, financial stress, and infidelity, among others. This issue affects not only the couples themselves but also their children, families, and the wider community, emphasizing the need for a deeper understanding of the factors influencing marital satisfaction and the development of effective strategies to promote it. Married individuals in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas struggling with marital dissatisfaction may display heightened arguments and verbal hostility, leading to a decline in communication and emotional disconnection, reduced affection and emotional bonding, resulting in a lack of warmth and emotional nurturing, and a surge in unfaithfulness, causing psychological distress and adversely affecting their children's quality of life, ultimately undermining the very fabric of their relationships and family units.

Marital satisfaction can be evaluated from the perspectives of both husbands and wives' point of view. To Laurenceau & Barrett (2005), several factors are said to influence both husband and wife's marital satisfaction. To them, these factors include level of intimacy, the ability to self-disclose with their spouses and perceiving their partners as responsive. Other factors of wife's view include husbands' expression of affection and amount of time spent together, as well as communication styles. Factors associated with marital satisfaction from the husbands' point of view include satisfaction with sexual relationship, marital satisfaction, commitment, division of household tasks or view of gender roles and the extent of input they perceive in the relationship. Hicks and Platt (2000) reported that factors such as marital happiness, family size, age, occupational status of husband and wife are considered important. Other studies (Carlson and Stinson, 2001) indicate that age has an increasing positive effect on marital satisfaction, that is, the higher the age of marriage, the better the outcome in terms of marital satisfaction.

One of the major aims in marriage is to fulfil a variety of human needs such as generation survival and upbringing of children, fulfilling the dream of being parents, achieving the highest level of friendship and intimacy, labour division, cooperation, assisting one another, having a safe place for peace and flourishing skills as well as achieving human perfection, elevation and mental health (Sadrolashrafi 2011). Human expectancy, generally, is to achieve happiness through marrying someone and forming a married life (Jamshidi, 2015).

Demographic variable is a sociological term indicating personal characteristics of individuals. It is categorization of people according to their economic, educational and family characteristics. It is defined as the social standing or class of an individual or group. They are used to identify and categorize individuals or groups based on various attributes, such as age, gender, marital status, occupation, income level, education level, race, ethnicity, and geographic location. Demographic variables such as age, gender, education level, income, occupation and family size have been identified by Tyowua and Hinga (2019) as influential factors in shaping marital satisfaction.

Gender, to Olurode (2013) refers to the social, cultural, and psychological attributes and behaviours that a society considers appropriate for men and women. Unlike sex, which is biologically determined, gender is a complex social construct that varies across different cultures and historical periods. It encompasses roles, responsibilities, and expectations placed on individuals based on their perceived masculinity or femininity.

Gender as a demographic variable, has been a topic of significant research in the field of marital satisfaction. In heterosexual relationships, gender roles and expectations can influence how individuals perceive their roles within the marriage. Gender inequality and disparities in power dynamics can be associated with lower marital satisfaction. Studies carried out by Doherty, (2019) have found that a more egalitarian division of household and childcare responsibilities tends to be associated with higher levels of marital satisfaction. Additionally, the impact of gender is not limited to heterosexual couples; same-sex couples may experience unique dynamics related to gender that can affect their satisfaction (Kurdek, 2005). However, gender has long been identified in the literature as a predictor of marital satisfaction (Bernard, 2003). Specifically, early works suggested that men report being more satisfied with their marriages compared to women in both Western and non-Western cultures (Rostami, 2014).

In many societies, the roles of gender are deeply entrenched and influence various aspects of life, including personal identity, social interactions, and access to resources and opportunities, gender roles are significantly shaped by traditional beliefs and cultural practices. For instance, in many communities, men are typically seen as the primary breadwinners and decision-makers, while women are often expected to take on domestic responsibilities and caregiving roles. Couples who develop effective communication skills, such as active listening and empathy, report greater satisfaction.

Family size, according to google encyclopaedia, is considered from two perspectives. At the individual (micro) level, it defined one aspect of an individual's family background or environment while at the societal (macro) level, family size is an indicator of societal structure that may vary over time, with concomitant implications for individual development and social relations in different cohorts (Family Size, (nd)). In the context of the Tiv people, a subgroup in Nigeria, cultural nuances, and preferences regarding the gender composition of children further add complexity to the dynamics between the family

size and marital satisfaction. Research by Aondofa and Iorwuese (2018) emphasized the significance of the family size as a key determinant of marital satisfaction among the Tiv people. The Tiv, like many other cultures, place considerable importance on family size and composition as farmers, the more the children, the more the labour force on farms. Specifically, among the Tiv, the gender of children holds cultural relevance, with a particular emphasis on the importance of having male children as they are often considered essential for the continuity of the family lineage, the preservation of family name, and the inheritance of family wealth (Orhungur, 2016).

This cultural expectation may introduce unique dynamics into marital relationships, influencing the perceived satisfaction based on the gender composition of offspring. Furthermore, research findings by Tyowua and Hinga (2019) indicated that among the Tiv people, couples with a balanced mix of male and female children reported higher levels of marital satisfaction. The cultural value placed on having male children can contribute to increased satisfaction when this preference aligns with the actual gender distribution in the family. However, it is important to note that discrepancies between the desired and actual gender composition of children may lead to stress and dissatisfaction within the marital relationship. Couples who do not achieve the desired balance may experience challenges in meeting cultural expectations, potentially affecting their perceived marital satisfaction (Akpenpuun, 2020). It is on this ground that the researcher is investigating demographic variables as correlates of marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Marital satisfaction is a crucial component of a stable union and the desire of every couple unfortunately most marriages in the study area seems not to enjoy their marriages leading to increased divorce, separation, infidelity and many other marital crises leaving couples, would-be couples, children and parents worried. Studies indicate that it is increasingly being influenced by shifting socioeconomic, cultural, and demographic factors. In Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State, reports of marital dissatisfaction suggest that evolving expectations regarding gender roles, income disparities, education, and family structures may be contributing to relationship strain. While studies like Amato and Chiwogu (2016) highlight the positive correlation between education and marital satisfaction in Western contexts, the Nigerian reality differs significantly, as traditional norms often frame higher female educational attainment as a disruption to marital power dynamics (Onah & Achonu, 2018). Additionally, economic factors remain a major stressor in marriages, as research by Fawole (2003) indicates that financial disparities and extended family obligations heighten marital strain. In Vandeikya and Konshisha, where financial responsibilities often extend beyond the nuclear family, it remains unclear how specific demographic variables such as age difference, gender, occupational level, family size, education, and income disparities contribute to marital satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Despite extensive research on marriage and family dynamics in Nigeria, limited empirical studies have examined these factors in the specific socio-cultural context of Vandeikya and Konshisha LGA. This study seeks to fill this gap by investigating how these demographic and economic factors interact to shape marital satisfaction. The findings will provide data-driven insights that could inform marriage counselling practices, family policies, and strategies for fostering healthier marital relationships within these communities.

Research Questions

The study will be guided by the following questions;

1. How does gender relate to marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State?
2. In what way does family size relate with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses have been formulated to be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Gender has no significant relationship with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State.

2. Family size has no significant relationship with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study was the descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised of two local governments namely Vandeikya and Konshisha with a total number of 4,140 married couples. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 365 respondents that constituted the sample. Ten council wards were purposely selected from twenty-three (23) council wards from the total sample. Two instruments for data collection were used. These are researcher-developed questionnaires: Demographic Variables of Married Couples Scale (DVMCS) and Marital Satisfaction Scale (MSS). The questionnaire followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was that if the p-value is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the null hypothesis should be rejected, but if proven otherwise, it should not be rejected.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *How does gender relate to marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State?*

Table 1: PPMC Analysis of Relationship between Gender and Marital Satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State

		Gender	Marital Satisfaction
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	989**
	N	365	365
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	989**	1
	N	365	365

Table 1 reveals that $r = 989$, $N = 365$. This indicated that there was a positive relationship between gender and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State. This implies that, as gender factors are related to marital satisfaction.

Research Question 2

In what way does family size relate with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State?

Table 2: PPMC Analysis of Relationship between Family Size and Marital Satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State

		Family Size	Marital Satisfaction
Family Size	Pearson Correlation	-1	-896**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	365	
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	-896**	-1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	365	365

Table 2 reveals that $r = -896$, $N = 365$. This indicated that there is a negative relationship between family size and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State. This implies that, as family size increases, marital satisfaction reduces.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: Gender has no significant relationship with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Gender and Marital Satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State

		Gender	Marital Satisfaction
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.989**
	P-value (Sig. (2-tailed))		.000
	N	365	365
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.989**	1
		.000	
	N	365	365

Table 3 reveals a correlation coefficient between gender and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State with, $r = .989^{**}$ and $P\text{-value} = 0.000$. Since $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between gender and marital satisfaction is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that gender has a significant positive relationship with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 2: Family size has no significant relationship with marital satisfaction among couples among Couples.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Occupation and Marital Satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State.

		Family size	Marital Satisfaction
Family size	Pearson Correlation	-.681**	-.681**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	365	
Marital Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	-.681**	-.681**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	365	365

Table 4 reveals a correlation coefficient between family size and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State with, $r = -.681^{**}$ and $P\text{-value} = 0.000$. Since $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between family size and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State is rejected. This implies that family size has a significant negative relationship with marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

Hypothesis one revealed that there is a positive correlation between gender and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State. This finding aligned with Bernard (2003) and Rostami (2014), who reported that gender is a predictor of marital satisfaction, with men often reporting higher satisfaction than women across various cultures. The strong positive correlation in this study supports this perspective, indicating that gender differences significantly shape satisfaction levels, possibly due to distinct roles and expectations. However, it contradicts Doherty (2019), who found that egalitarian gender roles, rather than gender itself, enhance marital satisfaction by fostering balanced responsibilities. The divergence from Doherty’s findings may reflect the specific socio-cultural context of Vandeikya and Konshisha, where traditional gender norms might still dominate,

amplifying gender's direct influence on satisfaction rather than its mediation through egalitarianism. The strong correlation observed can be justified by the cultural dynamics prevalent among the Tiv people in Benue State. In Tiv society, gender roles are deeply entrenched, with men typically viewed as breadwinners and decision-makers, while women are often relegated to domestic and caregiving roles (Olurode, 2013). These traditional expectations may create distinct experiences of marital satisfaction for men and women, where fulfilment of culturally prescribed roles enhances satisfaction, thus explaining the near-perfect correlation.

Hypothesis two revealed that there is a negative correlation between family size and marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria. This suggests that as family size increases, marital satisfaction tends to decrease among these couples. The strength of the correlation, being moderately strong, underscores a notable inverse relationship between these two variables. This finding aligns with Kowal et al. (2021), who established that an increase in the number of children can negatively affect marital satisfaction due to added stress and resource demands. However, it contrasts with Tyowua and Hinga (2019) who found that among the Tiv people, family size and composition positively influences marital satisfaction when cultural expectations (e.g., having male children) are met. The divergence from Tyowua and Hinga's findings reflect the broader scope of family size in this study, which includes total number of children and dependents, rather than focusing solely on gender composition, potentially overshadowing cultural preferences with practical burdens. The negative relationship observed can be justified by several contextual factors pertinent to Vandeikya and Konshisha. In these rural agrarian communities, larger family sizes may traditionally be valued for labour support in farming, as noted by Aondofa and Iorwuese (2018). However, modern economic pressures, such as limited income and resources (highlighted by Oyekale and Adeoti, 2016), could strain couples' ability to manage larger households, leading to reduced marital satisfaction. Additionally, the increased responsibilities and time demands associated with raising more children might detract from spousal intimacy and communication key factors in marital satisfaction according to Laurenceau and Barrett (2005) explaining why the finding leans toward a decline in satisfaction as family size grows. This interplay of cultural expectations and contemporary socioeconomic challenges likely drives the observed outcome in these specific locales.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated demographic variables as correlates of marital satisfaction among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State. The findings revealed a positive relationship with gender and negative relationship of family size among couples in Vandeikya and Konshisha Local Government Areas of Benue State.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendation were made for counsellor to educate spouses on gender equality stressing that female children are equal to male children and Counsellors to educate couples on family planning and stress management.

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